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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ACUTE PURULENT DESTRUCTIVE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Despite the decrease in the total number of children suffering from complicated course of pneumonia and the development of modern technologies of diagnostics and therapy, the problem of tactics of treatment of destructive processes in the lungs does not lose its relevance. The article summarizes the clinical experience of diagnostics and treatment of destructive pneumonia in 124 children. The presented algorithm makes it possible to diagnose in time and provide necessary therapeutic interventions, including mini-invasive interventions, to children with pulmonary and pleural complications of the course of pneumonia

Key words: Acute purulent-destructive pneumonia, early diagnosis, concomitant therapy

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ОСТРАЯ ГНОЙНО-ДЕСТРУКТИВНАЯ ПНЕВМОНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Несмотря на снижение общего числа детей, страдающих осложненным течением пневмонии, и развитие современных технологий диагностики и терапии, проблема тактики лечения деструктивных процессов в легких не теряет своей актуальности. В статье обобщен клинический опыт диагностики и лечения деструктивной пневмонии у 124 детей. Представленный алгоритм позволяет своевременно диагностировать и оказывать

необходимые лечебные пособия, включая мини-инвазивные вмешательства, детям с легочными и плевральными осложнениями течения пневмонии

Ключевые слова: Острая гнойно-деструктивная пневмония, ранняя диагностика, сопроводительная терапия

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BOLALARDA O'TKIR YIRINGLI-DESTRUKTIV PNEVMONIYA

ANNOTATSIYA

Pnevmoniyaning asoratlardan jabr chekayotgan bolalarning umumiy sonining kamayishi va zamonaviy diagnostika va terapevtik texnologiyalarning rivojlanishiga qaramay, o'pkadagi destruktiv jarayonlarni davolash taktikasi muammosi o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotmaydi. Maqolada 124 bolalarda o'tkir yiringli pnevmoniyani tashxislash va davolashning klinik tajribasi umumlashtirilgan. Taqdim etilgan algoritm pnevmoniya kursining o'pka va plevra asoratlari bo'lgan bolalarga o'z vaqtida tashxis qo'yish va zarur terapevtik imtiyozlarni, shu jumladan mini-invaziv aralashuvlarni taqdim etish imkonini beradi

Kalit so'zlar: o'tkir yiringli-destruktiv pnevmoniya, erta tashxis, hamrohlik qiluvchi terapiya

Introduction. Despite the decrease in the total number of children suffering from complicated course of pneumonia and the development of modern diagnostic and therapeutic technologies, the problem of treatment tactics for destructive processes in the lungs does not lose its relevance. Late diagnosis and tendency to excessive conservatism in therapy against the background of modern drugs, on the one hand, eliminate the etiologic factor of inflammation, and on the other hand, cause an increase in morphologic manifestations of the disease. The lack of clear algorithms of treatment of various forms of pulmonary destructions and their complications, depriving the possibility of correct and timely intervention in the focus, has an impact.

Today, the diagnosis of bronchopulmonary diseases is based on radiography, computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging, and ultrasound (USG) [1,2,4].

There are a large number of different methods of treatment of destructive pneumonias in children. The choice of adequate, complex, pathogenetically based therapy often determines the prognosis of the disease [5, 6].

Currently, most pediatric surgeons have revised their attitude to radical lung surgeries in children with acute purulent destructive processes. Along with the improvement of conservative intensive and antibacterial therapy, a number of modified surgical methods aimed at sanation of purulent destructive focus have been proposed in recent years. Surgeons have focused special attention on the development and introduction into practice of organ-preserving methods of endoscopic surgery, sparing and minimally traumatic surgical interventions [3, 7, 8].

Aim of the study: To present a modern approach to treatment of purulent and destructive processes in children's lungs.

Material and methods of the study: 124 children with destructive pneumonias were treated in pediatric surgery department of Andijan city for the last 3 years. Age of patients ranged from 1 month to 18 years. The majority of children (124 patients) were admitted from different hospitals, 24 children - after outpatient treatment. The terms of the disease by the time of hospitalization in the department were 5-11 days.

Of 124 children, lobular abscess was diagnosed in 40 patients, macroabscesses were observed in 10 children, giant cortical abscess - in 1 child. Pleural complications were detected in 70 patients.

On the background of pleurisy and fibrin deposits, hydrothorax was observed in 21 cases, pyopneumothorax - in 32 cases, pyothorax - in 9 children.

We examined 2 patients with mediastinal complications: purulent mediastinitis - in 2 patients, purulent pericarditis - in 1 patient. Pulmonary hemorrhage occurred in 1 patient, including 1 case of bleeding into pleural cavity. Septic condition was noted in 6 children.

In addition to physical and laboratory data the leading method of examination in the diagnosis of destructive processes in the lungs is traditionally radiography. According to a number of characteristic radiologic symptoms it is possible to formulate a fairly accurate diagnosis.

Figure 1 Microabscess, macroabscess. Giant cortical abscess

However, in some cases, especially in massive pleural deposits, it is difficult to reliably assess the presence and nature of the effusion in the pleural cavity, which makes it difficult to determine further treatment tactics. Ultrasound of the thoracic cavity is of particular value in such situations. Scanning is performed both from the subcostal access and through the intercostal spaces. The disorganized fluid component in the pleural cavities looks like anechogenic content. Fine suspension is often observed in purulent nature of the effusion. Thin, sometimes mobile structures usually correspond to fibrin filaments and appear when the effusion is organized (Fig. 1). Polyposition scanning along the intercostal spaces allows to reliably assess the drained accumulations of effusion.

Figure 2. Fibrinothorax

In controversial cases, especially in the presence of focal changes in the lungs and pleural cavity, CT may be performed.

Results of the study. Inflammation localized within one lung lobe, which was in the infiltrative stage of its development, did not belong to destruction and required intensive treatment, sanitation drainage measures, the ultimate goal of which was to achieve an abortive course of the

process. In case of further disease development the infiltrate entered the next stage of inflammation - abscessation.

Abscessing of the lobitis developed in two directions - with and without drainage into the bronchus. In the first, the most favorable variant a course of bronchoscopic sanitation and continuation of conservative treatment were indicated, the second variant required peribronchial catheterization of abscess and, if successful, bronchoscopic sanitation. This manipulation was performed in 17 patients. The use of ultrasound monitoring allowed to control the effectiveness of the procedure in real time without harming the patient and the staff. In 2 cases of unsuccessful per-bronchial lavage we performed thoracocentesis with transthoracic drainage of the focus of purulent inflammation. After the last manipulation there was an improvement of the child's condition with subsequent recovery, but in 1 child a bronchopleural fistula was formed, which required blockade of the leading bronchus for up to 14 days and continuation of intensive post-syndromic therapy.

Precursors of destructive process development - subpleural microabscesses - were detected in 16 children, they were treated conservatively. In 2 cases, microabscesses formed macroabscesses on the background of progressive destructive process.

Macroabscesses, observed in 9 patients, as well as giant cortical abscess, which we met in only one observation, were managed similarly to abscessed lobitis.

Treatment of pleural complications included ultrasound of the lung and pleural cavity at the stages of diagnosis. This necessity arose primarily due to the difficulties of differential diagnostics between hydro- and fibrinoto-rax, which in a number of cases made it possible to refuse the so-called diagnostic pleural punctures.

In the presence of hydrothorax, pleural puncture was performed in 10 patients. This procedure was also supplemented with ultrasound monitoring.

Purulent effusion can be drained, shrouded or total. In pyothorax 4 patients underwent thoracoscopy with ultrasound sanitation and drainage of the pleural cavity 1 child was admitted late in the disease with formed bronchopleural fistulas, collapsed lungs, which was a contraindication to thoracoscopy.

Pneumothorax and pyopneumothorax required pleural cavity drainage with Bullough aspiration in 33 patients. In case of lung expansion and in the absence of active air discharge, conservative treatment was continued. If the lung did not collapse and there was still air discharge through the drainage, the question of bronchoblockade was solved, which was performed in 4 patients.

In case of fibrinothorax, when the disease duration did not exceed 10 days, 16 patients underwent thoracoscopy with closed decortication of the lung and ultrasonic sanitation of the pleural cavity in antibiotic solution. Fibrinothorax with disease duration more than 10 days was a contraindication to thoracoscopy because of dense fibrinous adhesions between parietal and visceral pleurae, separation of which may lead to complications.

Among other complications of the course of destructive pneumonias in 5 children we met septic processes - purulent mediastinitis in 3 patients during anterior mediastinum drainage using flow-flush drainage system and purulent pericarditis in 2 patients, which required fenestration and drainage of pericardium performed thoracoscopically in 1 child destructive pneumonia was complicated by pulmonary hemorrhage, which was stopped conservatively. Among chronic forms of destructive pneumonia outcome in 1 child we observed fibrothorax, treatment of which lasted about 7 months, but did not require surgery and ended with recovery.

Secondary lung cysts were formed in 2 children, of which the cyst was localized in S6 on the right side and disappeared within 3 months of follow-up, in the other case the cyst was located subpleurally in the projection of the lingual segments, it was removed from the thoracoscopic access after 4 months of patient's follow-up.

Conclusions

1. Application of ultrasound monitoring of lungs and pleural cavities in children with destructive pneumonia allows controlling the effectiveness of therapeutic manipulations and significantly reducing the radiation load on the patient.

2. single-port thoracoscopy with ultrasound sanation of pleural cavity in antibiotic solution allows to free the lung from fibrin plaques, deliver antibacterial drug to the focus of inflammation, remove inflammatory exudate.

3 The use of mini-invasive interventions in the treatment of purulent-destructive processes in the lungs of children allows to refuse traumatic methods of surgical treatment and significantly reduce the risk of further complications.

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